

Communicating Russia: Analysis of Latvia's Experience (ComRu)

Version 1

Description

The focus in the project is communication in Latvia's public space about Russia and the things that have been and are still occurring since Russia's full-fledged invasion of Ukraine. The relevance of the research project is based on Russia's special role in Latvia's political and cultural space and in awareness of same, as well as on the fact that Russia's role in the Latvian public space is a phenomenon that is complicated, multi-layered and ambiguous. The study will analyse long-time linguistic, cultural and information practices transformations since Russia's full-fledged invasion of Ukraine. The theoretical framework of research consists of the theoretical approaches of cultural othering, colonization, decolonization, collective memory, and media/medium and message. During the implementation of the project, it is planned to prepare two scholarly articles on the topic of the project, to present research results at conferences, in popular publications, to include newly created knowledge in study course content and policy recommendations.

Funder

European Commission | EC

Grant

EU Recovery and Resilience Facility project "Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia" (No.

5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007)

Researchers

Vita Zelče (0000-0002-5169-8862)

Organizations

University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Communicating Russia: Analysis of Latvia's Experience \(ComRu\)](#)

Description:

The focus in the project is communication in Latvia's public space about Russia and the things that have been and are still occurring since Russia's full-fledged invasion of Ukraine. The relevance of the research project is based on Russia's special role in Latvia's political and cultural space and in awareness of same, as well as on the fact that Russia's role in the Latvian public space is a phenomenon that is complicated, multi-layered and ambiguous. The study will analyse long-time linguistic, cultural and information practices transformations since Russia's full-fledged invasion of Ukraine. The theoretical framework of research consists of the theoretical approaches of cultural othering, colonization, decolonization, collective memory, and media/medium and message. During the implementation of the project, it is planned to prepare two scholarly articles on the topic of the project, to present research results at conferences, in popular publications, to include newly created knowledge in study course content and policy recommendations.

Researchers:

[Vita Zelče \(0000-0002-5169-8862\)](#)

Organizations:

[University of Latvia](#)

Contact: [Zelče Vita \(vita.zelce@lu.lv\)](mailto:vita.zelce@lu.lv)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: [European Commission](#) | [EC](#)

Grants: [EU Recovery and Resilience Facility project "Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia" \(No. 5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007\)](#)

Project: [ComRu](#)

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

4. Templates

Descriptions

LCS FARP

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

2 Research Data Management

3 Resources and Security

LCS FARP

Representative sociological survey of the Latvian population about attitudes towards the Russia, and its culture

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

To determine attitudes of population of Latvia towards the Russia, its culture, celebrities, narratives and symbols

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Survey data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No similar data is available

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Sociologists, communication and cultural researchers, policymakers

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Till the date of publication

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

<https://zenodo.org>

Zenodo is general purpose repository for scientific results

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Excel, SPSS Statistics

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

No

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2027-01-03

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

The part of funds are allocated specifically to research data management

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Vita Zelče (0000-0002-5169-8862)

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

LCS FARP

In-depth interviews with producers, directors and experts about Russian culture and its communication in Latvia

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

In-depth interviews with producers, directors and experts about Russian culture and its communication in Latvia to find out their opinions and professional practices

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

PDF

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

200

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No similar data is available

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

For communication and culture researchers

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

01/03/2027

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Zenodo is general purpose repository for scientific results

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

PDF

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

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2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

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2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

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3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
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3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

Consent of the interviewee

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

LCS FARP

Oral history interviews with former teachers, as well as another people from the Soviet time

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Oral history interviews with former teachers, as well as people from the Soviet time world of culture to determine their attitude towards Russia, its culture and its communication in Latvia

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

PDF

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

a. 200

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No similar data is available

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

For communication, culture and education researchers

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

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2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

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No

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No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

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Euro

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3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

The views of interviewed people will not be published without their agreement

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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